

Disproof of the Principle and Theory of Relativity. Has the Michelson-Morley Experiment been Serving to Protect the Wrong Theory?

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Abstract

In this paper, the principle of relativity is disproved based on accepted experimental evidence and experience. We argue that the Michelson-Morley experiment is not a proof of relativity at all. In fact, in a complete surprise to the scientific community, the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment has been an effective 'hiding place' for the special theory of relativity.

Introduction

The null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment is widely accepted in mainstream physics as evidence for the principle of relativity. On the other hand, there are some experiments that seem to contradict the principle of relativity, such as experiments on the velocity of light relative to a moving observer. Next we present a disproof of relativity based on these experiments and accepted views.

Galileo's ship thought experiment

Consider a light source emitting a light pulse from some point in the Earth's frame, at $t = 0$. The velocity of the source is irrelevant. At the instant of light emission, an observer is at distance D from the source and is moving away from the source with velocity v , in the Earth's frame.

We know that the light will catch up with the observer at $t = D / (c - v)$. This is a well-known and accepted fact even in the Special Relativity Theory SRT and has been confirmed by experiments. Now I will use this in my argument against the principle of relativity.

Consider Galileo's ship thought experiment. An observer in a closed room of the ship does a physics experiment. There are two light sources S_1 and S_2 , with the distance between them equal to $2D$. The line connecting the sources is parallel to the longitudinal axis of the ship, and hence to the velocity of the ship. S_2 is in front of S_1 . A detector is placed at the midpoint between the sources, at distance D from each of the sources. The light sources each emit a short light pulse simultaneously every second. The detector detects the time difference between the pulses.

The observer in the closed room first has to synchronize the clocks at S_1 and S_2 . For this, a short light pulse is emitted from S_1 towards S_2 . Suppose that S_1 emits the light pulse at $t = 0$. The observer in the closed room (a relativist) synchronizes the clocks based on the principle of isotropy of the speed of light. However, unknown to him/her, we know that the clocks synchronized by this procedure will be out of synch by an amount:

$$\frac{2D}{c-v} - \frac{2D}{c} = 2D \frac{v}{c(c-v)}$$

The clock at S_2 will be behind the clock at S_1 by this amount.

It should be noted that, according to special relativity, the clocks synchronized by this procedure will be in synch. However, from experience we know that the clocks will be out of synch. I think even relativists implicitly accept this (i.e. the clocks being out of synch); they only claim that this does not contradict SRT, using inconsistent arguments as usual. Physicists usually describe SRT by using thought experiments in deep space, claiming that SRT is a correct theory of the universe. However, when it comes to terrestrial experiments, they usually switch their interpretation of SRT to a one that agrees with experimental outcomes. Note that in the above Galileo's thought experiment, we assumed a terrestrial experiment. However, if a relativist was given the same problem, except that the experiment is done in deep space, he/she would say that the clocks will be in synch. Therefore, we know that the relativistic procedure is wrong, based on experience and inconsistency in the analysis of SRT. Therefore we analyze the experiment classically as follows.

The sources each emit a short light pulse 'simultaneously' (quoted because the clocks are not actually in synch), every second. The observer in the ship expects the pulses to arrive simultaneously, which they do not.

Let S_1 emit the light pulse at $t = t_0$. Then S_2 will emit 'simultaneously' at time

$$t_0 + 2D \frac{v}{c(c-v)}$$

The light from S_1 arrives at the detector at time

$$t_0 + \frac{D}{c-v}$$

The light from S_2 arrives at the detector at time

$$\left[t_0 + 2D \frac{v}{c(c-v)} \right] + \frac{D}{c+v}$$

The difference in the time of arrival of the two pulses at the detector will be:

$$\Delta = \left[t_0 + 2D \frac{v}{c(c-v)} + \frac{D}{c+v} \right] - \left[t_0 + \frac{D}{c-v} \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta = \frac{2D}{c} \frac{v^2}{c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

The relativist observer synchronized the clocks, placed the detector at the midpoint between the sources and the sources emitted light pulses 'simultaneously'. He/she would expect the light pulses to arrive simultaneously at the detector, which they didn't. The light pulses always arrive with a time difference of Δ . The observer would have no way to explain this. To any one rejecting this argument, my response is this: let an actual experiment be done to test it.

We know that the origin of the problem lies in the observer assuming isotropy of the speed of light while synchronizing the clocks. Moreover, this value (Δ) is not constant. Suppose that the ship is initially moving at some steady velocity and the observer measures Δ based on the above synchronization procedure (assuming isotropy of light speed). Then the ship is accelerated to a new steady velocity and Δ is measured again by the same procedure. The two Δ 's will be different. This is because, unknown to the observer, who believes in relativity, Δ depends on the velocity of the ship in some reference frame (at least in the frame of the sea). Therefore, even though the observer followed the same procedure in both cases, he/she will get a different value of Δ in each case, depending on velocity. This would violate the principle of relativity. The observer would then have to abandon the principle of relativity in order to understand the origin of Δ .

Is the principle of relativity completely wrong?

With the above argument, we have disproved relativity. At this point one might still wonder how Galileo's cherished principle of relativity could be wrong. If the mystery of motion and the speed of light has eluded 21st century physicists, how couldn't it have eluded Galileo, who lived in an era when man had little knowledge of the physical universe. The nature and speed of light, (absolute) motion and quantum phenomena is so extremely subtle and elusive that it has eluded generations of scientists since Galileo.

On the other hand, however, the principle of relativity is not completely wrong. Although it is fundamentally wrong, it is a very good approximation to understand ordinary, everyday physical phenomena in which velocities much less than the speed of light are involved. For example, Newton's laws of motion and gravitation, which are based on Galilean relativity, apply with a high degree of accuracy in most systems, such as planetary systems. In fact, it is the many successes of the principle of relativity that led physicists to think that it is a fundamentally correct law of nature, which it is not.

The Michelson-Morley experiment – an experiment that has been effectively protecting a wrong theory

We have decisively disproved both the principle of relativity and the special theory of relativity in the above argument, by a correct analysis of experimental evidence. However, there has always been one obstacle to all attempts to disprove relativity, whether logically, mathematically or experimentally: the null result of the Michelson-Morley (MM) experiment. The MM experiment has been the single most important factor for the continued acceptance of relativity theory, because it protects the foundation of special relativity, which is the principle of relativity.

Absolute motion has been detected with several experiments. I am not even talking about the small effects observed in the Miller experiments, which is a second order experiment. The Silvertooth experiment, the Marinov experiment and the Roland de Witte experiment have all clearly detected large first order effects. So far the theory of relativity has defied all these experimental evidences and continues to be a mainstream theory.

Here I reveal for the first time how relativity theory is doing this. Relativity theory has so far defeated all attempts to disprove it by ‘hiding’ behind the null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment. The extremely subtle and elusive nature of (the speed of) light has helped relativity theory in this. The mystery is that the Michelson-Morley experiment does not actually disprove absolute motion. It is only incapable to detect absolute motion. The Michelson-Morley experiment was capable to detect the ether if the ether existed, but the ether doesn't exist, hence the null result. The mystery is a distinction between motion relative to the (non-existent) hypothetical ether and absolute motion. Not surprisingly, the two have always been used synonymously by the physics community. That the scientific community assumed that the Michelson-Morley experiment proves the principle of relativity is not surprising at all . In fact, it would be surprising if the scientific community thought otherwise.

This is what has made disproving relativity theory so difficult. The null result of the Michelson-Morley experiment has been an extremely elusive hiding place for the theory of relativity. It has been an effective shield to protect the foundation of special relativity, which is the principle of relativity, from any attack.

One might ask: if absolute motion is not motion relative to the ether, then what is absolute motion? I propose that absolute motion arises from motion of an object relative to all matter in the universe.

I have already proposed a theory [1] that can provide a compelling alternative explanation not only to the Michelson-Morley experiment, but also to the Sagnac effect, the Silvertooth and the Marinov experiments, stellar aberration, moving source and moving observer experiments, moving mirror experiments, the Lunar Laser Ranging (LLR) experiment, the Venus planet radar ranging experiment anomaly (Bryan G Wallace), the Ives-Stilwell experiment, Einstein's chasing a beam of light thought experiment, constancy of the speed of light relative to all observers, and other experiments.

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References

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